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INTRINSIC DRIVERS: MEDIATING THE IMPACT OF TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE REWARDS ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR IN MUMBAI'S TEXTILE FIRMS

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ABSTRACT

This research paper explores the influence of tangible and intangible rewards on intrinsic motivation & Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) in the textile firms of Mumbai. Using a sample of 173 employees from 06 textile firms, the study employs a quantitative approach to analyse how different types of rewards impact OCB and how it impacts intrinsic motivation. The findings aim to provide valuable insights for organizational leaders and policymakers in the textile industry, highlighting the importance of tailored reward systems to enhance employee engagement and organizational performance.

Introduction

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) refers to voluntary, extra-role activities that employees undertake to benefit the organization (Organ, 1988). These behaviors, while not formally rewarded, significantly contribute to organizational efficiency and cohesion (Podsakoff et al., 2000). In the context of the textile sector in India, where competitive pressures and labor-intensive processes dominate, understanding what drives OCB is crucial for maintaining a productive and motivated workforce (Singh, 2018).

Tangible rewards, such as bonuses, salary increments, and other financial incentives, have long been used to motivate employees (Armstrong, M., 2009, Gerhart & Rynes, 2003). These rewards directly impact employees' economic well-being and are often considered primary motivators for performance (Milkovich & Newman, 2002). On the other hand, intangible rewards, such as recognition, career development opportunities, and a supportive work environment, cater to employees' psychological needs, fostering a sense of belonging and purpose (Kuvaas, 2006).

Intrinsic motivation, the inner drive to perform tasks for their inherent satisfaction, can play a pivotal role in linking rewards to OCB (Daniel, T.A. and Metcalf, G.S. 2005, Ryan & Deci, 2000). While tangible rewards can spark initial motivation, intrinsic motivation sustains long-term engagement and commitment to OCB (Deci, Koestner, & Ryan, 1999). This study seeks to fill the gap in existing literature by analysing how both tangible and intangible rewards influence OCB and intrinsic motivation in the textile sector of India (Bhatnagar, 2014).

Despite numerous studies examining the direct effects of rewards on employee behaviour, few have delved into the interplay between different types of rewards and intrinsic motivation, especially within the Indian textile industry (Jaiswal & Dhar, 2016). This study aims to address this gap, offering insights into how organizations can effectively leverage both tangible and intangible rewards to enhance OCB through fostering intrinsic motivation (Kaur, 2019).

Research Framework

Hypothesis:

On the basis of literature support following hypothesis were formulated:

H1: There is significant relationship between Tangible rewards and OCB.

H2: There is significant relationship between intangible rewards and OCB.

H3: There is significant relationship between Tangible rewards and intrinsic motivation.

H4: There is significant relationship between intangible rewards and intrinsic motivation.

Sample Size

The study employs a quantitative research design, collecting data through structured questionnaires distributed to 173 employees across 06 textile firms in Mumbai. Sample consisted of Quality Control Managers, Team Leaders, Floor Supervisors, Technical Specialists and Textile Engineers. The questionnaire was designed to measure perceptions of tangible and intangible rewards, levels of intrinsic motivation, and the extent of OCB exhibited by employees.

Correlation was studied through Software (SPSS 20.0). To measure reliability of scales Cronbach's alpha has been used.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were first used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the sample and the primary variables of interest. Correlation was studied through Software (SPSS 20.0). To measure reliability of scales Cronbach's alpha has been used.

Reliability and Validity Testing

The reliability of the measurement instruments was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The constructs for tangible rewards, intangible rewards, intrinsic motivation, and OCB all demonstrated high reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.70. This indicated that the items within each construct were consistently measuring the same underlying concept.

Research Instrument:

The instruments used for the study are reward system questionnaire (Al, Nsour., 2012), OCB was measured using Lee and Allen (2002) - Short Form consisting of 8 items, intrinsic motivation was measured by using Short Form of the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI) by was used to study Intrinsic Motivation of employees. It was

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developed by Edward L. Deci, Richard M. Ryan, and their colleagues in 1985 as part of their work on Self-Determination Theory (SDT).

Cronbach's alpha

Cronbach's alpha of the scale used to measure rewards is .866 ($\alpha=.876$) whereas for OCB it is .852 ($\alpha=.825$) and for intrinsic motivation it is .866 ($\alpha=.866$)

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows that tangible rewards and OCB are significantly positively correlated, $r=.58$, $p<.01$.

Pearson Product moment correlation among the tangible rewards and OCB (N=173):

Variables	1	2
Tangible Rewards	-	.58**
OCB	-	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 2 shows that intangible rewards and OCB are significantly positively correlated, $r=.68$, $p<.01$.

Pearson Product moment correlation among the intangible rewards and OCB (N=173):

Variables	1	2
Intangible Rewards	-	.68**
OCB	-	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 shows that tangible rewards and intrinsic motivation are significantly positively correlated, $r=.70$, $p<.01$.

Pearson Product moment correlation among the tangible rewards and intrinsic motivation (N=173):

Variables	1	2
Tangible Rewards	-	.70**
Intrinsic Motivation	-	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 4 shows that intangible rewards and intrinsic motivation are significantly positively correlated, $r=.76$, $p<.01$.

Pearson Product moment correlation among the intangible rewards and intrinsic motivation (N=173):

Variables	1	2
Intangible Rewards	-	.76**
Intrinsic Motivation	-	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

The present study investigated the influence of tangible and intangible rewards on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and intrinsic motivation within the textile companies. With a sample of 173 employees data was collected through structured questionnaires, aligning with previous literature indicating a significant correlation between rewards and job satisfaction (Pinder, 1984). The findings robustly supported the study's hypothesis, revealing that both tangible and intangible rewards positively influence OCB among workers.

The study highlighted that while both types of rewards contributed positively to OCB, intangible rewards exhibited a more substantial effect. This underscores the pivotal role of psychological and social incentives in fostering extra-role behaviors within the textile industry. Workers were evidently motivated by factors beyond financial remuneration, emphasizing the importance of intrinsic motivation in translating rewards into meaningful contributions to organizational success.

In particular, the results indicated that intangible rewards such as recognition, praise, and opportunities for personal growth played a critical role in enhancing OCB and intrinsic motivation. Employees who felt valued and appreciated were more likely to engage in discretionary behaviors that benefit the organization beyond their formal job roles. This aligns with theories of organizational behavior emphasizing the importance of supportive work environments and psychological empowerment (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Moreover, the study highlighted the complementary nature of tangible and intangible rewards. While financial incentives are essential for meeting basic needs and expectations, intangible rewards sustain motivation over the long term. The findings suggest that organizations in the textile sector should adopt a balanced approach, integrating both types of rewards to maximize employee engagement and productivity (Saqib et al., 2015).

The implications for practice are clear: organizations should cultivate a supportive and recognition-rich environment to leverage the full potential of their workforce. Strategies could include implementing formal recognition programs, fostering a culture of appreciation among supervisors, and providing opportunities for skill development and career advancement. These initiatives not only enhance job satisfaction but also contribute to a positive organizational climate conducive to high levels of OCB and intrinsic motivation (Pouliakas, 2008).

In conclusion, the study underscores the significance of rewards, both tangible and intangible, in shaping employee behaviour and organizational outcomes in the textile sector. By understanding and leveraging these motivational factors, organizations can enhance their ability to attract, retain, and motivate talented employees, thereby achieving sustainable competitive advantage in a dynamic market environment.

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Conclusion

This research contributes to the understanding of how different types of rewards influence OCB through intrinsic motivation in the Textile firms. The findings suggest that a balanced approach, incorporating both tangible and intangible rewards, is essential for fostering intrinsic motivation and enhancing OCB. For organizational leaders and policymakers, the study provides actionable insights on designing effective reward systems that not only incentivize performance but also cultivate a motivated and committed workforce. Future research should explore these dynamics in other sectors and cultural contexts to validate and extend these findings.

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